

FINE ARTS IN SUGHD IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES

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Annotation: Before Central Asia came under the influence of the Arab Caliphate, visual and applied arts were developed in the region. Especially in Sughd, it is known that high results were achieved in architecture, painting, sculpture, stone and wood carving, calligraphy, music and other arts. This is confirmed by the discovery and research of the ruins of Kafirkala, Afrosiyab, Varakhsha, and Panjikent . Among these, the ruins of Panjikent, the center of the early medieval Panch principality, show the development of various artistic styles in this region.

Key words: Art, Afrosiyab, Panjikent, Vaarakhsha, Kafirkala, early Middle Ages becomes more clear.

The images found in the ruins of the city of Panjikent are considered an important source in the study of visual art in early medieval Sughd, and are distinguished by the fact that they are well studied by specialists in the field to this day. Therefore, it was decided to refer more to Panjikent murals in the study of the network of visual arts in Sughd.

We know that the cities of Central Asia, such as Afrosiyab, Panjikent, Varakhsha, Kafirkala, fell under fire and lost their existence. Of course, as a result of this fire, the murals have not reached our days. The ones that arrive are also damaged, so their analysis is based on more guesswork.

Taking the Panjikent murals as an example, the remains of Panjikent murals were found in temples, residential buildings, and administrative structures that were public places. Fragments of mural paintings found in the remains of temples in particular show how important religion was among the people of Panjikent. In

the north-east of the city of Panjikent, the remains of two side-by-side temples were found, which were located in the urban part of the city.

These temples consist of multi-functional buildings, long corridors connecting them, and porches decorated with murals. In the center of the temples is the mihrab, which is kept in the fire. It is a large square hall, and the walls of the hall are decorated with murals. According to A.Yu.Yakubovsky, the murals of the temple had a religious and secular content ¹.

As a result of subsequent researches, Afrosiyab, Panjikent, Varakhsha, and Kafirkala mural paintings are divided into religious, artistic, and folklore genres in terms of subject and content (except for murals depicting animals) ².

The representation of the image of a four-armed deity is not new to the art of Central Asia. A similar image of the goddess was also found in Panjikent. For example, his image in the building number 5/16 inside the Panjikent temple has not reached us in its entirety. Many elements that reveal its characteristics have migrated. The image depicts a four-armed god sitting on a dragon-shaped throne with a river flowing beneath his feet and various creatures in the background behind the throne. The four-armed deity has sun and moon symbols on his hands. Also, in this image, silver goblets and examples of Khorezm writing indicating that these goblets were made in Khorezm are also shown.

N.V.Dyakonov and O.I.Smirnova conducted research on this mural and interpreted it as the deity of Nana, who was already known in Sughd.

Researchers believe that Nana deity (goddess) is the patron of the city of Panjikent ³. It is probably a hint that the river flowing under the feet of the goddess is the Zarafshan river.

Decorating them with the goddesses of other countries in Sughd painting means that this art form is related to other countries both ideologically and in terms

¹ Yakubovsky A.Yu. Voprosy izucheniya Pyandzhikentsk o y jivopisi // Jivopis drevnogo Pyandzhikenta. Moscow: Iskusstvo, 1954. S. 12.

² Belenitsky A.M. Monumental art Pendjikenta. Live sculpture. ... S. 42.

³ Belenitsky A.M., Marshak B.I. Chert y mirovozreniya Sogdiytssev VII - VIII vv. v iskusstve Penjkenta S. 12.

of color imagery. It is not difficult to understand that the deities of other countries are depicted by the image on the walls of the buildings numbered VI/8 and VII/124. It depicts the dancing god Shiva in blue. The image of the three-headed deity on the wall of building number XXII/1 is implicitly associated with the goddess Shiva, and these three-headed deities are called "Trimurti". One of the deities depicted in it is Lord Brahma, the other is Shiva and the next is Vishnu, and the distinction between Shiva in the middle is probably to indicate that he is the creator and finisher of the whole world.

The analysis of fine art samples shows that the people of Central Asia, including Sughd, worshiped different religions before the conquest of the Arab caliphate. The above examples confirm this. The remnants of religious views such as Zoroastrianism, Monism, and Buddhism presented in the images indicate the transformation of these religions. This was certainly taken into account by the artists.

Let's go back to the question of the characteristics of fine art in murals. Sughd was also one of the regions where military work developed. Among the murals of Panjikent, you can also observe women soldiers in special action. On the wall of residence No. VI/42, a woman warrior fighting with a man is depicted. Indeed, it is known that in the history of Central Asia, there have been brave women like Tomaris and Zarina ⁴.

It is known from Mugh Mountain Sugdian documents that in Sugdian society, citizenship is divided into 3 categories: officials, merchants, and workers ⁵. It is exactly this category of merchants that the artist has brilliantly depicted with the help of a brush. Ras Som was able to highlight party and everyday wear. The fact that the people in the picture are in a party position shows this.

It is important that visual art in Sughd strives to reflect every situation in society. In addition to drawing pictures of individuals and heroes of the work, -

⁴Goyibov B. Cultural and domestic life of the people in Panjikent murals. ... B. 38-42.

⁵SDGM II. S. 94-95.

Sogdian artists also painted unknown objects, animals, and images related to the folklore genre. It should be noted that there are views related to the depiction of the examples of fine art in Sughd by the Monites. At this point, it is necessary to give information about it.

the course of research that Sughd painting influenced not only the oasis of Zarafshan, but also the whole of Central Asia . Afrosiyab, Varakhsha, and Panjikent murals, some of which have been painted with their colors, have survived to this day. So what kind of paint did they use? Painters got color from natural minerals. For example, a special mixture - tree glue, animal and fish bone glue was mixed from the red soil to ensure its adhesion . They used gypsum and coal for white paint. And for black

Thus, by the time of the early Middle Ages, fine art and applied art, which have been going on since ancient times, continued on the basis of local traditions and developed under the influence of Indian, Greco-Roman, Chinese, Arab-Persian cultures. Although visual art declined somewhat during the reign of the Arab caliphate, it continued beyond Sughd and served as the foundation stone for the later, well-developed visual art of the Middle Ages.

